

Alternative Protein Sources in the Giant Leaps AltProt-P Study

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Food name	Photo	Wikipedia link
Legumes		
Adzuki bean (red mung bean) (<i>Vigna angularis</i>)		Adzuki bean - Wikipedia
Black-eyed pea (also known as cowpea) (<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>)	<p data-bbox="660 1543 1102 1576">Reproduced courtesy of Wikimedia</p>	Cowpea - Wikipedia
Butter or Lima bean (<i>Phaseolus lunatus</i>)	<p data-bbox="660 1895 1166 1995">Reproduced courtesy of Howard F. Schwartz, Colorado State University, Bugwood.org, CC BY 3.0 unported licence</p>	Lima bean - Wikipedia

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Chickpea (<i>Cicer arietinum</i>)		Chickpea - Wikipedia
Common bean. Varieties include Black bean, borlotti bean, <u>cannellini beans</u> , cranberry bean, flageolet bean, haricot bean, navy bean, pinto bean, red kidney bean (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>)		Common bean - Wikipedia
Fava bean (also known as fava broad, field, horse or tic bean) (<i>Vicia faba</i>)		Fava bean - Wikipedia

<p>Lentil (<i>Lens culinaris</i>)</p>	<p>Reproduced courtesy of Rainer Zenz, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons</p>	<p>Lentil - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Mung bean (green gram) (<i>Vigna radiata</i>)</p>		<p>Mung bean - Wikipedia</p>

<p>Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>)</p>		<p>Pea - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Urad bean (black gram) (<i>Vigna mungo</i>)</p>		<p>Urad bean - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Seeds and vegetables</p>		
<p>Butternut squash (<i>Cucurbita moschata</i>)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As flesh • As seed 		<p>Butternut squash - Wikipedia</p>

<p>Chia seed (<i>Salvia hispanica</i>)</p>		<p>Chia seed - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Coconut (<i>Cocos nucifera</i>)</p>		<p>Coconut - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Flax seed (<i>Linum usitatissimum</i>)</p>		<p>Flax seed - Wikipedia</p>

<p>Hemp seed (<i>Cannabis sativa</i>)</p>		<p>Hemp seeds - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Jackfruit (<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>)</p>		<p>Jackfruit - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Kenari nut (<i>Canarium indicum</i>)</p>	<p>Adapted from Muséum de Toulouse, CC BY-SA 3.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0>, via Wikimedia Commons</p>	<p>Canarium indicum - Wikipedia</p>

<p>Makhana seed (lotus seeds, fox nut (<i>Euryale ferox</i>))</p>		<p>Lotus seed - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Pili nut (<i>Canarium ovatum</i>)</p>	<p>Reproduced courtesy of Lance Catedral from Quezon City, Metro Manila, Philippines, CC BY-SA 2.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/2.0>, via Wikimedia Commons</p>	<p>Canarium ovatum - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Pumpkin or squash (<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>) :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As flesh • As seed 	<p>Reproduced courtesy of Daniel Schwen, CC BY 3.0</p>	<p>Pumpkin - Wikipedia</p>

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<p>Sunflower seed (<i>Helianthus annuus</i>)</p>		<p>Sunflower seed - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Quinoa (<i>Chenopodium quinoa</i>)</p>	<p>Reproduced courtesy of Fumikas Sagisavas, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons.</p>	<p>Quinoa - Wikipedia</p>

Other		
Chlorella		Chlorella - Wikipedia
Duckweed, water lentil <i>(Lemna gibba and Lemna minor)</i>	<p data-bbox="600 1167 1166 1234">Reproduced courtesy of Kostka Martin, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons.</p>	Lemnoideae - Wikipedia
Moringa leaf or powder <i>(Moringa oleifera)</i>		Moringa - Wikipedia
Mushroom	<p data-bbox="588 1888 1174 1955">Reproduced courtesy of George Chernilevsky, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons</p>	Mushroom - Wikipedia

<p>Noni fruit (<i>Morinda citrifolia</i>)</p>	<p>Reproduced courtesy of Wilfredor, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons</p>	<p>Morinda citrifolia - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Other algae (e.g. <i>Euglena gracilis</i>)</p>		<p>Euglena gracilis - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Quorn</p>		<p>Quorn - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Seaweed</p>		<p>Seaweed - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Spirulina</p>		<p>Spirulina - Wikipedia</p>

Insects		
<p>Cricket (<i>Acheta domesticus</i>)</p>		<p>Cricket - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Mealworm (<i>Tenebrio molitor</i>, <i>Alphitobius diaperinus</i>)</p>	<p>Reproduced courtesy of Tony Webster - Mealworms in Jar, CC BY 4.0, https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=177432730</p>	<p>Mealworm - Wikipedia</p>
<p>Other type of insect</p>	<p>Reproduced courtesy of Jnpet, CC BY-SA 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>, via Wikimedia Commons</p>	<p>https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Insects_as_food#Edible_insects</p>